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Efficient ways of direction the students to the research work in the classes of Informatics (from the work experience)

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Abstract. Theoretical and practical methods of designing mentioned in project works, which can be applied in practical classes for increasing the teaching efficiency are considered in the work.

Key words: teach, Informatics , project works, project.

In the 4th part of the Message of the Head of our country N.A. Nazarbayev “Strategy “Kazakhstan-2050”: New political course of the formed state” “Knowledge and professional skills are main direction of the system of modern education, personnel training and retraining” it was said: “In order to be a developed competitive state we should turn into the highly educated country. ... Our citizens should be always ready to master their skills working with the most advanced equipment in the most modern manufactures. Also we should pay much attention to the functional competence of our children and generally all rising generation. It is very important for our children to be adopted to the present time.” In this concept the particular significance was pointed to the education, competence and qualification of the youth and future specialists [1].

I believe that Informatics subject will open the way for gaining all-round education for our future generation as well as for their free development of businesslike and talent, intelligent and creative skills. One of the methods of this concept implementation is arrangement of project works in the classes of Informatics and in extracurricular time.

Setting the purpose “To create the conditions for formation research capacity which encourages the development of creative and logical thinking of students”, I marked out the following tasks to be solved. They are:

1. To develop pupils cognition ;

2. to increase the interest in study;
3. to train independent study as well as development skills;
4. to find out right things in the information space and develop selection abilities;
5. to teach students to reflection;
6. to train to speak in public;
7. to form thinking abilities from critical point of view.

Taking into consideration the necessity to direct the students purposely and systematically in their project work and to encourage them to see the results of their own work, I have been arranging project works in the field of programming mastering lately in my experience. On the base of my observation I think that carrying out project researches, namely making students plan and do complicated tasks is efficient in mastering their knowledge in Informatics.

I represent the stages of project creation in the following “Project cycle” diagram. Here I divided the project work arrangement into 4 stages, and every stage consists of several parts as it was presented in picture 1.

Picture 1. Project cycle

Table 1.

Content of the project stages

States of the project work	Content of the work	Basic activities of the teacher in the solution of the educative purpose	Students activities
Preparation stage	To determine the theme and the purpose of the project. Dividing into groups.	Encourages students to select the theme within one direction. Teaches to plan taking into consideration the opinion of every student in the group.	Every student leaning on his own life experience (if it is available) shares his opinion and joining together determines the final purpose of the project.
Planning	To show the ways of gathering and selecting information. To identify the work of every member of the group. To plan the work	Guides the students to collect the information independently. Listens to the decision of the collective discussion taking into account the opinion of every student, and in case of necessity shares his opinion. Checks the student's diary on the project.	Determine the work of every member of the group, define the time of achieving the first results planning the stages of working out their own theme. Show their readiness to execute the task. Creates the sample of the project.

1. Creation the project	To work under the project	Guides and gives advice supervising the student's diary, talking to every supervisor and member of the group, analyzing, comparing the results. Calls to solidarity, to respect each other.	Carry out individual and pair work
2. Discussion the results. Evaluation	To analyze the information, to make up a decision, to plan the form of the presentation.	Encourages to defeat jointly the project and to see the results of the work by evaluating the job of the individual students in the group. Creates the opportunity for students to speak and to think critically by listening, asking problematic questions. Evaluates the creative work and leads the students to the highest goals.	Identify the problematic issues and get ready to solve them jointly. Listen to each other very carefully, follow every one's opinion taking into account the culture of speaking. Defend the project, learn to evaluate themselves.

If I present the example from my own work experience about arrangement of project creation, it is thought that in every particular lesson planning a mini-project it is possible to turn it into a big one. As the following projects:

I. Creation the project “Calculator” in the Delphi medium.

The project is created in 3 classes.

For example:

1- class. It is planned as a project to find out the sum of two numbers.

2- class. It is completed by equipping with the calculator to execute the way 4.

3-class. It is completed and finished by using the menu.

II. During the process of the next class one of the applied programs is thought to be planning of the individual program. The project work is organized within 7 classes. The project is organized individually or in pair in accordance with the students wish. "Projects auction" is held for project defeat. It can be held once a year. My students really like it. In my students' opinion (reflection):

1. every student can express himself as a creative person,
2. everybody can execute the job that he likes,
3. the tradition to perform independent work is formed,
4. develops the tradition to represent himself, to define himself as well as to execute his own abilities and opportunities,
5. becomes educated to responsibility, to respect, to share his own opinion, to be tolerant, to work in group,
6. learns to evaluate his own job and the work of other students.

The projects that won in the "Projects auction" are processes, completed and prepared with the purpose to take part in various levels competitions.

Finally, I can make the following conclusion in my experience during the process of teaching and education and in extracurricular time .

Mastering the knowledge with the help of arranged project research works in the system under the programming course in the class of Informatics is thought to be significant in the development of the personality of the student, represent the student in future in various situations and any social environment as well as in adoption to the life. This is because the following qualifications are formed at the students that will be necessary in the future:

- they can choose the theme independently according to their abilities and interests.
- they can analyze independently the content of their work on the base of the set purpose.
- they look for the ways to achieve and to carry out the purpose assigned independently.
- they create the conditions to check and to develop the abilities and the limit of abilities.
- they learn to collect the information and to think systematically and critically.
- they can select the efficient methods of work by analyzing and comparing approaches.
- they get used to speaking in public, to delivering their own opinion by proving

and in the logical way, to attracting the attention of the audience.

- they get used to listening to other people's points of view and to analyzing and considering the forwarded issues.

- they know how to solve the complicated problems on their own.

- they try to convince the listeners of their right decision by proving their own opinion.

Organization of the project work

First of all, encourages the students to solve various problems, to become ready-witted and to apply to new scientific researches by improving the creative abilities of the students and their desire to research, to develop their cognitive interests,

secondly, I was convinced in my own practice that the method of projects is thought to be one of the most efficient innovation technologies, and

thirdly, it gains the opportunity to take part in the city, regional competitions,

fourthly, the integrity of subjects is formed,

fifthly, it uses the opportunities of the programming medium in other subject competitions.

Of course, at any level of education the lack of skills of independent work, organization of study and actions can cause problems, thus, I hope that the presented experience will be useful by investigating theoretical and practical bases of the programming method.

References:

1. Message to the people of Kazakhstan of the Head of our country N.A. NAZARBAYEV "Strategy "Kazakhstan-2050": New political course of the formed state", Astana city, December 14, 2012.